

Flora and vegetation of Recif Island (Seychelles) and the management of seabird populations

by

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SUMMARY

Based on a review of the literature, plant specimens available in herbaria, and a field trip done to Recif Island from the 21st to the 24th of October 2024, we compile the checklist of the flora of the island and a description of the vegetation and terrestrial ecosystems.

The flora contains 19 species. The typology of ecosystems contains 9 ecosystem-types distributed in 6 Ecosystem Functional Groups of the new IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology.

Using a PlanetScope image (5m resolution, for October 2024) and an aerial image provided by the Government of Seychelles (0.5m resolution, from 2010), we then produced a map of the distribution of the different ecosystem-types (at 1m resolution).

Based on those findings, we then discuss the situation of the seabird populations, in relation to the vegetation patterns. We conclude that, in the current state of knowledge, the best option is not to establish large scale vegetation management actions, but rather to set up carefully designed new experimental surveys in order to :

- evaluate the effect of *Cyperus ligularis* density on the Sooty tern nesting density,
- quantify the biomass trend over a few years for the *Cyperus ligularis* grassland,
- and to measure the expansion rate of the *Nephrolepis biserrata* patches.

In addition, we recommend compiling existing data (from 2006 onwards) on circular plots (nesting density) so to evaluate the population trend of the Sooty terns on Recif Island.

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Cover page images: **Top**, View of the plateau and granitic hill from the South-East coast, showing the limestone deposits (the smooth flat surface) topping a deposit of phosphatic sandstone largely dismantled by the waves action; **Bottom**, Same view but from the center of the plateau showing an anchialine pool cut into a limestone karst reaching up to ca. 1.5-2m above high water level.

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I INTRODUCTION

I.1 Objectives

This study aims at providing a finer understanding of the ecosystem functioning of Recif Island, primarily in view of the Sooty tern (*Onychoprion fuscatus*) population management. In particular, the Biodiversity Conservation and Management Division (BCM) of the Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE) has hypothesized that the Sainte Marie sedge (*Cyperus ligularis*) acts as an invasive species affecting the bird population and they are looking for vegetation management options that could potentially improve the nesting habitat of the Sooty tern colony.

I.2 Study area

Recif Island (official name: Ile aux Récifs) is a small granitic island of just 16.3 ha (based on the island outline as updated in this study). It is fairly isolated between Mahé (27km), Praslin (24km), La Digue (22km) and Frégate (18km). Its northern part (12.1ha) is a granitic hill 45m high (sometimes called “Upper Récif”) and its southern part (4.2 ha) is a flat plateau (sometimes called “Lower Récif”).

One of the most remarkable aspects of Récif is that it has been neglected by most visitors. This island being small and on the way to more ‘interesting’ islands, it seems that only birds have attracted some attention. Baker (1963), in his geological survey, did not visit the island, and botanists have only contributed 7 plant species records (Robertson 1989). Other interesting records include a few arachnids: *Nesiergus halophilus* (Theraphosidae) and *Chiromachus ochropus* (Liochelidae) (Justin Gerlach, in Senterre et al. 2012).

The island is cat-free and rat-free and the only reported invaders are the rabbits, whose population seems to be reduced and concentrated on the lower slopes of the granitic hill. Since 1994, Recif is managed by the Biodiversity Conservation and Management Division (BCM) of the Department of Environment with a focus on the Sooty terns, as part of a broader monitoring of bird populations in Seychelles. Annual reports have been produced until 2004 under the direction of Chris Feare, of which the most relevant for Recif are: Feare and Gill (1994, 1995); Feare (2002). Other useful reports that we could access and that provided useful information on Recif include: Dine and Esparon (2005); Gendron (2006).

During the trade wind season, from May to September, birds come in great numbers to reproduce on the island, corresponding to a period of more abundant foraging resources. Throughout that season, the BCM team ensures presence in the field for both the monitoring of the bird populations and for the prevention of egg poaching. Seven seabird species breed on the island, among about 10 species listed (Bristol 2002, 2003; Feare 2002) and their respective spatial distribution has been described (Figure 1). Sooty terns occupy mostly the upper and flatter areas of the hill, where they nest between the clumps of an open tussocky grassland (80% of ground cover, 0.5m high, when occupied by the birds), while it generally prefers more open habitats on other islands, with more bare soil and shorter vegetation. They share that habitat with the Common noddies (*Anous stolidus*, often nesting on slightly elevated rocks or vegetation). On the slopes, we find the two Shearwater species (Wedge-tailed Shearwater *Puffinus pacificus* and Audubon’s Shearwater *Puffinus bailloni* subsp. *nicolae* (previously cited as *Puffinus lherminieri*), nesting in burrows in the soil or beneath rocks) and the Bridled terns (*Onychoprion anaethetus*, nesting within tussocks of Sainte Marie sedge or under the shelter of rocks). Finally, on the plateau, Lesser noddies (*Anous tenuirostris*) dominate and nest at 0.25 to 2m above ground in the branches of a dense *Scaevola taccada* shrubland, as well as in the few isolated or clumped trees. They share that habitat with the White terns (*Gygis alba*).

Figure 1. Existing maps on the distribution patterns of seabird populations on Recif Island: (a) by Feare (2002), showing Sooty Tern colony in June 2002 (diagonal hatching), Bridled Tern colony in June 2002 (horizontal hatching) and Bridled Tern colony in February 2003 (shading, source Rachel Bristol, 2003); (b) by Gendron (2006).

Figure 2. Existing maps on the vegetation of Recif Island, developed by Gendron (2006), and updated by the same author in 2018.

The vegetation of Recif is almost shockingly treeless. Indeed, other islands of the granitic group with important seabird populations (such as Aride) are wooded to some extent. The same is true with very small granitic islands such as Mamelles, Ile Ronde, etc. In fact, the question of the naturalness of the landscapes of Recif comes very quickly, and especially the question of the place of trees on that island. The most complete description is found in Feare (2002). At that time, the idea had emerged that some vegetation management could include the creation of woodlands in some areas, firstly to support seabird species nesting in trees (such as the Lesser noddies) or even to provide the environment for the introduction of some island endemic land birds (considering the rat-free character of Recif: see Feare 2002). Although Feare (2002) provided a very insightful discussion of the question and recommended to abandon that idea, about 1500-2000m² of trees were planted in the plateau area (in 2012). Those areas have now become sparse clumps of trees, about 5-6m high.

In 2006, a map of the vegetation was done by Gendron (2006), and later updated by the same author in 2018 (Figure 2). It describes about 9 different vegetation types. On the granitic hill, Gendron (2006) recognized the 'Sedge', 'Sedge & rock' and the 'fern' types. On the plateau, she recognized a 'Veloutier' zone mostly on the edges of the plateau while the larger area of the plateau was labelled 'Other vegetation'. The remaining classes were relatively localized. Finally, the rocky shores were distinguished in both the plateau and the hill sides of the island.

As pointed out by Feare (2002), those early studies on the flora and vegetation of Recif Island needed to be complemented by the visit of specialists, so to confirm the plant species occurring on the island, and to discuss the vegetation into more details. The current report is addressing that recommendation.

II METHOD

II.1 Field observation

A field trip was done to Recif Island from the 21st to 24th October 2024. The team included Gilberte Gendron, Shemilla Jeremie, Damien Labiche, Farah Nasser, Maryssa Samedi and Bruno Senterre.

Over 300 photographs were taken for the various habitats and landscapes of the island. Those were then analyzed and regrouped into a number of 'stands' for the purpose of ecosystem description and mapping (Figure 3).

We collected 20 botanical specimens (BS 7507 to BS 7524) corresponding to 15 species and representing the complete flora of the islands at present. Those have been deposited at the Seychelles National Herbarium (SEY) in 2 to 3 copies (depending on phenology state).

In parallel, all flora and fauna observed were recorded and uploaded onto iNaturalist (onto Beeecological account). Annex 1 provides a summary of all non-plant species observed.

We also took a number of GPS points for the verification of the georeferencing of remotely sensed images, and we tracked all our exploration paths on the island using a smartphone Huawei P30 Pro and the Android app SWMap.

Finally, the field trip was the opportunity to have many discussions with the BCM team and to explore the various aspects of the current study.

Figure 3. Aerial image (from 2010) of Recif Island, indicating the exploration tracks (in blue) and observed stands of vegetation (red dots). The black line is the pre-study outline of the island.

II.2 Mapping of ecosystem-types

Image selection and preparation

Due to the small size of the island and the fine grain of the vegetation patterns, we combined one infra-metric image provided by the Government of Seychelles (at 0.5m resolution, RGB), with an image from PlanetScope NICFI (at 5m resolution, RGB plus near infrared). The former is dated from 2010, while the later was for October 2024.

To select the best image from PlanetScope, we reviewed all monthly mosaics available since 2023 and selected the best one, at the same time closest to the dates of our field work. The details on the image selection process can be seen in more details in the Earth Engine script `develop` for this study.

The selected PlanetScope image as well as the Government image were then downloaded locally, and loaded in a QGIS project, together with our ground truthing and georeferencing data. The two images were georeferenced to align on the field georeferencing data (note that the Government image was already well georeferenced, and so all we did was to align the PlanetScope image, which was not).

Then, we manipulated the two georeferenced images in R and compiled them into a single image, containing all 4+3 bands as well as a band giving the altitude (based on online global dataset, namely SRTM, at 30m resolution). All bands were resampled at 0.5m resolution (i.e. to the original Government image resolution). We also masked the resulting image to a polygon shapefile that we created manually following the exact coastline as per the most detailed image available (the Government of Seychelles image). This will avoid having to deal with ocean pixels during the image classification process.

Image classification (multispectral analysis)

Finally, the resulting image was uploaded back into Earth Engine and used to create an image classification. Three spectral indices were used based on PlanetScope bands (NDVI, NDWI, EVI) and one was based on the Government image (GLI). Full names and definitions for the spectral indices used can be found here: <https://www.indexdatabase.de/db/is.php>.

We then developed a supervised classification using 9 classes with a pixel-based image analysis (as opposed to object-based) using the `randomForest` algorithm.

Post-classification modifications

The resulting classification image was exported from Earth Engine and further modified locally using expert knowledge. We edited the raster manually using the QGIS plugin `ThRasE`. After installing the plugin, we created one window with the classified image, the aerial image from the Government, and our GPS tracks from the field. Then we played with transparency ordering of the layers to reclassify zones of pixels that were misclassified, such as for example, Sainte Marie sedge pixels identified in the plateau and corresponding in fact to Vouloutye shrublands at a slightly lower density. With `ThRasE`, it is possible to define a polygon and reclassify all or any pixel class inside that polygon to another class.

III RESULTS

III.1 The flora

The flora of Recif Island is extraordinarily small. It contains 19 species, of which 1 is an old record of an introduced plant that has now disappeared (*Amaranthus dubius*), and another old record is likely a misidentification (*Fimbristylis cymosa*). Of the 17 species remaining, only 10 are native to the island, while the others (sometimes native to Seychelles) have been introduced on Recif (Table 1). This represents about 0.6 native species per hectare. As a comparison, Cousin Island (another small granitic island with breeding seabird populations), has three times more species per hectare (1.9 native plant species per hectare: 55 native species for 29ha; see Seychelles Key Biodiversity Areas National Coordination Group 2022).

Throughout the hill part of Recif (which represents the three quarters of the island area), we have only 7 species present (all native), of which one is largely dominant (Sainte-Marie sedge). On the plateau, we have 9 species, of which only 3 are native. Interestingly, virtually no native species is shared between the plateau and the hill floras (apart for some local edge effects).

Some additional species have been mentioned such as Zepi ble (*Stachytarpheta* sp., likely as a misidentification of *Heliotropium indicum*), Bwa taba (*Tournefortia argentea*, known misidentification of *Nicotiana tabacum*), and *Cassythia filiformis* (Ridley & Percy, 1958, likely extirpated sometime before 1994). Other interesting observations are found in by Bristol (2002).

Table 1. Checklist of the flora of Recif Island based on the compilation of historical specimens, literature and observations done during the current study. Specimen's numbers are indicated next to the abbreviated collectors "BSGG" (Bruno Senterre & Gilberte Gendron).

Species	Creole name	Origin	Habitat-use	References
<i>Acrostichum aureum</i>	Fouzer lanmar	Native	Coastal backshore, on the granitic hill	BSGG 7509, 7516
<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	Bred malabar, Brède parétaire	Introduced		Robertson (1989)
<i>Boerhavia repens</i>	Patate cauvin	Native	Coastal backshore and inland rock cliffs	BSGG 7523; Robertson (1989, as <i>B. coccinea</i>)
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Pie koko	Introduced	Coastal plateau	
<i>Cordia subcordata</i>	Porse	Introduced	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7519
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	Vatangue	Introduced		Robertson (1989)
<i>Cyperus ligularis</i>	Sainte-Marie Sedge	Native	Inland granitic hill	BSGG 7510; Robertson (1989)
<i>Fimbristylis cymosa</i>		Native		Robertson (1989)
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	Lerb papiyon	Introduced	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7517
<i>Ipomoea pes-caprae</i> subsp. <i>brasiliensis</i>	Patatran rouz	Native	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7524
<i>Morinda citrifolia</i>	Bwa torti	Introduced	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7521
<i>Nephrolepis biserrata</i>	Fouzer taba	Native	Inland granitic hill	BSGG 7511
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Taba	Introduced	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7522
<i>Pisonia grandis</i>	Mapou	Native	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7518
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> var. <i>oleracea</i>	Kourpye	Native	Coastal backshore, on the granitic hill	BSGG 7513-7515
<i>Scaevola taccada</i>	Vouloutye	Native	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7525
<i>Sporobolus virginicus</i>		Native	Coastal backshore, on the granitic hill	BSGG 7508; Robertson (1989)
<i>Stenotaphrum micranthum</i>	Herbe la seine	Native	Coastal backshore and inland rock cliffs	BSGG 7512; Robertson (1989)
<i>Thespesia populnea</i>	Bwa-d-roz	Introduced?	Coastal plateau	BSGG 7520; Feare (2002, p.6)

III.2 Vegetation, habitats and ecosystems typology

Similarly to the treatment of ecosystem-types proposed recently in a similar report for the Seychelles (Senterre et al. 2023), we propose to organized the ecosystem-types of Recif according to the two most important gradients related to the interface between ecological realms, namely the coastal-inland gradient and the upland-wetland gradient. Subsequently, we develop the conceptualization of the ecosystem-types recognized on the basis of other local gradients such as topo-edaphic wetness. We also integrate the bird-vegetation interactions in the ecosystem conceptualization through the concept of “ornithogenic disclimax”. The concept of “disclimax” (see more details in Senterre and Wagner 2014) describes ecosystem-types that have a dynamics that appears to be stuck in an early progressive state, due to the inherent effect of a disturbance factor that defines the ecosystem-type itself, such as the presence of birds to a level that leads to massive trampling and deposition of feces on plant leaves, etc. (Jones et al. 1994, 1997; Ellis 2005; Smith et al. 2011; Smyshlyaeva et al. 2021).

For each ecosystem-type, we propose a brief description, illustrations, and also the possible position within the Global Ecosystem Typology now being used by the IUCN (Keith et al. 2022). Broad synonymies (or correspondences) with previous vegetation mapping of Recif is also included. When necessary, a note is included to discuss uncertainties on the nature of a given ecosystem-type.

III.2.1 COASTAL FRONTSHORE

The coastal frontshore zone is the area under the direct influence of daily tides (supratidal zone) and/or sea sprays. It generally extends over a narrow strip, ca. 10-20m inland, although it can cover a broader area on exposed windward coasts. It is then followed, landward, by the backshore zone which can also extend more or less broadly, depending mostly on microtopography and hydrology. On Recif, the coastal frontshore zone is generally less than 10m broad. In the plateau area, it is contracted due to the slightly elevated phosphatite and limestone deposits still in place.

[1] Rocky shores and coastal cliffs

The shores of Recif are entirely rocky, with only small sand deposits in some places. On the plateau, we have a few areas of large granite pebbles (most granite pebbles are in the intertidal zone) and everywhere else the shore is made of a slightly raised (just above daily high tide level) plateau of phosphatic sandstone (on the west side: Figure 4) or limestone (which tops intertidal remains of phosphatic sandstone on the east side: Figure 5). Finally, all around the granitic hill of Recif, the shore is made of granite boulders and cliffs (Figure 6), rarely including small bays with granite pebbles at the bottom of the cliff (Figure 7).

Although botanically poor, the island of Recif offers an outstanding geological and geomorphological diversity, with several features not seen in any other island of the granitic group.

Synonymies: Rock outcrops (Gendron, 2006)

IUCN typology: MT1.1 Rocky shores

Note: Although the different types of lithologies (granite pebbles, granite cliff, phosphatic sandstone, and limestone) are visually quite distinct, we do not distinguish them at the scale of local ecosystem-types. We can argue that the dominant effect of the coastal frontshore exposition overrules those relatively minor nuances.

Figure 4. Rocky shores and cliffs ([1]) on the west coast of Recif, showing the slightly raised plateau of phosphatic sandstone (derived from Jemo soil series: Piggott 1968). The photo in the middle (almost at high tide: 22-Oct-2024, 5h58am, ca. 1h before 1.6m high tide) shows the raised position, as well as the undercut erosion of the cliff visible at low tide (top photo). The granite pebbles are located below the phosphatite, and at the lowest level of the low tide we can see some submerged (nearshore) beach rock (formed during lower sea level epoch).

Figure 5. Rocky shores and cliffs ([1]) on the east coast of Recif, showing the slightly raised plateau of limestone in the process of karst formation. Coral fossils are frequent, especially in the southern part. The photo in the middle shows the three main types of rocks found in that area: paleo-reef limestone, phosphatic sandstone, and calcarenite (paleo sand banks or mud flats). The photo at the bottom is taken near the granitic hill transition. It shows calcarenite blocks deposited on the surface of a limestone plateau with a slope oriented landward (as opposed to beach rock). Below it, we can see the brownish phosphatic sandstone being dismantled in the subtidal zone.

Figure 6. Rocky shores and cliffs ([1]) as typically seen on the shores of the granitic hill of Recif. In the photo in the middle, we can see the overlaying of phosphatite corresponding to the remain of a past forest cover (with developed soil and likely in association with seabirds for millions of years). The photo at the bottom shows the few areas where the granite pebbles constitute the supratidal rocky shore (mostly at the junction between the plateau and the hill).

Figure 7. Rocky shores ([1]), showing one of the few bays with granite pebbles on the northern part of the island.

III.2.2 COASTAL BACKSHORE UPLAND

The coastal backshore zone is the area under the indirect influence of the proximity to the ocean. It is influenced by the sea sprays but more rarely by tidal flushing. On large granitic islands such as Mahé, this zone is characterized by the “beach forest” (in the case of sandy shores).

[2] Coastal backshore subsaxicolous shrubland on raised limestone

The description of the rocky shores has emphasized a striking feature of the plateau area of Recif. It is not just phosphatic sandstone and guano deposits (like for instance on some plateau areas of Frégate or Cousin: Fosberg 1983). Rather, the phosphatic sandstone appears to be topped (likely over most of the plateau area) by raised limestone and karsts, giving in some places a look of ‘Aldabra’ (Figure 8). Therefore, over most of the plateau, the soil is skeletal and leaves little opportunities for tree development. Consequently, it is completely dominated by *Scaevola taccada* (Vouloutye) forming a dense shrubland 2-3m high. Would *Pemphis acidula* (Bwa damann) had the chance to reach this island, it would sure have colonized (invaded) the plateau and formed a dwarf forest at 5m high (or dense scrub if we use the terminology of the Aldabra group).

Synonymies: Veloutier; Veloutier & grass; Other vegetation (Gendron, 2006)

IUCN typology: MT2.1 Coastal shrublands and grasslands

Note: This ecosystem has an active dynamics influenced by occasional storm tides, leading to uprooting and dieback of large patches (such as after the 2004 tsunami, see Dine & Esparon 2005) followed by rapid recolonization. Depending on the soil depth, some areas are slightly higher and denser, or on the contrary sparser and with some exposed patches of karst.

[3] Coastal backshore woodland

There is only a handful of individual trees on Recif Island, most of which were planted in 2012 near the transition from the plateau to the hill. In that particular area, there is indeed more soil. In fact, we have observed small limestone cliffs (60cm high) parallel to that transition and which seem to be an ancient channel connecting to a backshore swamp and having been filled with sediments and guano. There are still likely some underground sea water fluxes which could possibly explain the narrow strip of bare soil located at the very edge of the hill (due to capillarity and hyper salinity effects), but more field work is necessary to confirm that.

In addition, it is important to note that the 4 or 5 individual *Pisonia* trees (which is likely the only native tree of Recif) are also located in the coastal backshore upland, more specifically in the western part of the plateau-hill transition zone. Those few trees are isolated within a patch of large granite boulders. We suggest that in a more or less distant past (centuries or millennia), the hill and plateau must have been covered by a *Pisonia* forest and that a catastrophic fire has, at some point, wiped it out. The geomorphology of the hill supports the idea of a forested past, and the peculiar position of the ‘relictual’ *Pisonia* trees (within huge granite boulders) supports the idea of a catastrophic fire (the granite boulders having played a protective role).

Near the centre of the plateau, there is also a single large *Pisonia* tree. It also occupies a peculiar situation, being sunk into a limestone cavity just the size of the tree crown. It is possible that this is the result of a relictual tree having survived some catastrophe and having subsequently facilitated the dissolution of the limestone, therefore further increasing its protective situation, and so on and so forth.

Synonymies: None

IUCN typology: T1.1 Tropical/Subtropical lowland rainforests

Note: Coastal forests or woodlands are not well treated in the IUCN typology. The recognized coastal ecosystems are all unvegetated, wetlands or grassy / shrubby formations (see MT2). We therefore have to use the class T1.1, and to consider the representatives on Recif as very degraded or relictual forms (therefore in a state that is not closed canopy, i.e. a forest, but sparse, i.e. a woodland).

[4] Coastal backshore *Sporobolus meadow*

On the granitic part of Recif, on the lower slopes of the hill, the coastal gradient can be observed much more easily than on the plateau. All around the granitic hill, a narrow belt, 0 to 20m broad, differs completely from the Sainte Marie sedge (*Cyperus ligularis*) meadows seen everywhere more inland. In that narrow coastal strip, the monodominant species is a grass (Poaceae) named *Sporobolus virginicus*. This is a typically coastal species, often found in coastal dunes (Fosberg and Renvoize 1980).

Occasionally, isolated patches can also be observed on the plateau edges, or on some of the sand deposits on the raised phosphatic sandstone or limestone plateau.

Synonymies: Veloutier & grass (Gendron, 2006)

IUCN typology: MT2.1 Coastal shrublands and grasslands

Note: Although nesting seabirds also occupy this habitat (the Shearwaters), the dominant filter driving this ecosystem is its coastal position, more than the ornithogenic influence.

III.2.3 COASTAL BACKSHORE WETLAND

[5] Coastal backshore anchialine pool

In the central part of the plateau, the karst is interrupted by depressions filled with mud and where the tidal influence is clearly visible. Interestingly, on the edges of those current wetlands we can see traces of fossilized wetlands, about 1.5m above maximum water surface level. Those are recognizable by the shape, size and angle of holes in the limestone and that correspond to the footprint of mangrove trees (Figure 8).

Synonymies: None

IUCN typology: SM1.2 Anchialine pools

Figure 8. Coastal backshore subsaxicolous shrubland on raised limestone ([2]) and Coastal backshore anchialine pool ([5]) observed in the plateau area of Recif Island. This landscape indicates that the central plateau area must have been a complex landscape of mudflats and mangroves (of which fossilized footprint can be observed), likely connected to the ocean through an outlet located near the junction plateau-hill, on the east side of it. The sea level at that point must have been just above the current limestone surface and the plateau might have looked similar to the current landscape observed at Cap Ternay (on Mahé), for example.

Figure 9. Coastal backshore woodlands ([3]). Although most of it corresponds to human introductions (some coconut trees in early days, and other coastal tree species in 2012), the few *Pisonia* trees are unquestionable natural and correspond to relict elements, being the only remains of some past catastrophic disturbances (very likely broad forest fire for the granitic hill, at the edge of which the few relict *Pisonia* trees are situated typically in the shelter of massive standing granite boulders). In the limestone plateau area, only a single *Pisonia* tree is observed sunk in a depression in the karst, the latter being either the cause of the tree presence or (more likely) the effect.

Figure 10. Coastal backshore *Sporobolus* meadow ([4]) observed on a 10-20m broad belt all around the granitic hill. This short grassland (or meadow) is entirely composed of a single species, covering 100% of the ground and reaching about 30-40cm high. The soil is skeletal and the lithology is granite or phosphatite.

Note: We suggest that considering anchialine pools as a transitional realm between Subterranean and Terrestrial realms is a mistake. It is the case for the underground caves connecting the pool to the ocean, but not for the pool itself.

III.2.4 INLAND UPLAND

Even though islands such as Recif are small and are sometimes considered as entirely “coastal”, they do show a clear coastal gradient, whereby most of the hill area can be considered as non-coastal (i.e. inland). In addition, no stream or other wetland exist in that area for Recif.

[6] Inland rocky outcrops and cliffs

In some areas of the summit and on the mid- and lower slopes, we observe some massive granite boulders (Figure 11), or granitic rocky soil, as well as different forms of phosphatite. Between those rocks, or at their edges, we observe typically *Nephrolepis bisserata* (Fouzer taba, at the edges of granite boulders), or *Stenotaphrum micranthum* – *Boerhavia repens* (Patate Cauvin) - *Portulaca oleracea* (Kourpye), within the phosphatized granite cliffs (Figure 12).

Synonymies: None

IUCN typology: T3.4 Rocky pavements, screes and lava flows

Note: The transition is of course poorly defined between the rocky outcrops and the nearby rocky meadows (see ecosystem [7]). We can nevertheless distinguish these two ecosystem-types (floristically) and they in fact do not pertain to the same Ecosystem Functional Group (EFG) of the IUCN typology. Therefore, the undifferentiation of transitions is not an argument for the recognition or rejection of the ecosystem-types being entangled in the landscape.

[7] Inland subsaxicolous ornithogenic tussock meadows

Besides rock outcrops (with little vegetation) and dense Sainte Marie sedge grasslands (see ecosystem [8]), the granite hill of Recif has many areas of moderate density Sainte Marie sedge on rocky soils. This distinction in density is not the result of ornithogenic influences (as is sometimes the case elsewhere, during the nesting season), but rather the result of different topo-edaphic constraints. Although it might appear, at first sight, as an insignificant distinction, it is in fact keystone to understand the broader landscape. These areas on rocky soil remain sparsely covered by the sedge throughout the year (while the ecosystem [8] has a peak of density at the end of the rainy season, before the beginning of the sooty tern nesting season). In absence of birds, and in presence of trees (but those were largely extirpated from the island), this ecosystem would ‘progress’ into a dwarf forest or woodland, similar to what can be observed on some areas of Cousin or Aride.

The biotic community is surprisingly entirely dominated by a single species (the Sainte Marie sedge – *Cyperus ligularis*), and only rarely can we observe isolated individuals of *Boerhavia repens* (Patate Cauvin), mostly near transitions to cliffs.

Synonymies: Sedge & rock (Gendron 2006)

IUCN typology: MT2.2 Large seabird and pinniped colonies

Note: This example and the one treated in the next ecosystem-type ([8]) illustrate the somehow problematic conceptualization of the IUCN class MT2.2. Indeed, large seabird colonies and their ornithogenic effects (guano deposits etc.) on the ecosystem can be observed in contrasted types of ecosystems, such as for example here in the grassland (with the Sooty terns) and in the plateau area *Scaevola* shrubland (for the Lesser noddies). Yet vegetation physiognomy is a key element of the IUCN typology and, in addition, other grassland disclimaxes (i.e. grasslands maintained due to an inherent disturbance factor, such as fire or grazing) are treated distinctively in the Functional Biome T4 (“Savannas and grasslands”). Not to mention that the coastal effect also appears as an important factor in the IUCN typology, while our study shows here that ornithogenic ecosystem-types spans an array of different environments from coastal to non-coastal (i.e. where more than one keystone ecological filter operates equally).

Figure 11. In the top photo, we see boulders of pure granite ([6] Inland rocky outcrops), without any trace of phosphatite or phosphatization. This means that those granite boulders have ‘always’ (in thousands and few millions of years) been protruding, and were never covered with forests. On the contrary, the smooth landform of most of the hill, with some isolated granite boulders clearly within a matrix of phosphatite (see middle and bottom photos) indicates that those other rocky areas ([7] Inland sloped subsaxicolous meadows) were not always exposed rocky areas but once covered by deep soil and forests (most likely *Pisonia*-dominated). Over time, at the contact of the granitic mother rock and the soil (Jemo serie), phosphatite rock formed.

Figure 12. Inland rocky outcrops and cliffs ([6]) showing here another type of rock formation commonly observed and consisting of granite having been phosphatized (e.g. in fissures; McKelvey 1967) and subsequently eroded differentially, resulting in sometimes spectacular polygonal shaped walls, used by seabirds for nesting. Those inland areas of phosphatized granite are often characterized by *Stenotaphrum micranthum*, *Boerhavia repens* (Patate Cauvin) and *Portulacca oleracea* (Kourpye), with only minor occurrences of the Sainte Marie sedge (*Cyperus ligularis*).

[8] Inland mesic ornithogenic tussock meadow

This is the most predominant and typical ecosystem-type of the granitic hill of Recif Island. The ground cover by rock is sufficiently low to allow the grassland to form a near continuous cover (ca. 80-90%). Only one plant species occurs, namely *Cyperus ligularis* (Sainte Marie sedge), which forms massive tussocks about 25cm diameter at base, interspaced by small areas largely covered by the spreading stems and leaves of the sedge. In most areas, the sedge reaches knee height (ca. 50-60cm), but in the more gentle sloped and less rocky areas (i.e. with the most optimal topo-edaphic wetness condition) it can reach hip height (ca. 70-80cm high). Even though the vegetation is dense, it is relatively easy to walk through by stepping between the tussocks. Birds also roam the area, and sometimes get stuck in the stems of the sedge (and die). This description is for the month of October, i.e. outside the Sooty terns nesting season. The grassland gets sparser and shorter at the peak of the nesting season.

Synonymies: Sedge (Gendron 2006).

IUCN typology: MT2.2 Large seabird and pinniped colonies

Note: This ecosystem is the most typical example of ornithogenic grassland. There is indeed no doubt that these areas (of mesic topo-edaphic nature, see Senterre 2014; Senterre et al. 2021) have a potential vegetation cover by forests. Similarly small granitic islands such as Mamelles or Round island have indeed no problem in having tree grooves and forested patches. Like other islands with massive nesting seabird populations (such as Aride or Bird island), the forest climax can be suppressed in some areas due to the birds effects (such as trampling, feces deposition on leaves, etc.). It is therefore necessary to consider this type of ecosystem as an ornithogenic disclimax, i.e. a grassland maintained as such by the continued effects of birds (or ‘disturbance’ from the plant point of view).

Figure 13. Inland ornithogenic tussock meadow ([8]), dominated by a single plant species *Cyperus ligularis*. In the bottom half of the photo, we can see (for the same season and same topo-edaphic conditions) the impact of the nesting birds on the vegetation.

[9] Inland progressive grassland

Besides typical observations at the edges of large granite boulders, we observed several large patches of *Nephrolepis biserrata* (Fouzer taba) in the middle of the densest areas of Sainte Marie sedge grassland ([8]). Those patches are all somehow circular in shape and vary in diameter from 4 to 40m. They are entirely dominated by the fern (without any other species) and are so dense that it is not possible to walk through it. The fern-dominated grassland (fernland) is about 1m high or more and very dense, without birds in it.

Synonymies: Fern (Gendron 2006)

IUCN typology: None

Note: Primary progressions are not well treated in the IUCN typology. Nevertheless, the ecological factors explaining this vegetation pattern are clearly related to a complex process with feedback loops, where the vegetation develops in slightly more favorable conditions (topo-edaphically), which leads to less birds using those areas, which then feeds back into the progression of the vegetation due to the suppression of the ornithogenic effects (trampling feces deposits, etc.), which in turn leads to fewer birds, and so on and so forth. If there were any pioneer tree species present on the island (or propagule sources not too far), these fernlands would soon develop some woody vegetation and expand faster by diffusion.

Figure 14. Inland progressive grassland on mesic phosphatic soil ([9]), dominated by *Nephrolepis biserrata*..

III.3 Ecosystem mapping

The map of ecosystem-types produced in this study is shown at Figure 15.

Figure 15. Map of the ecosystem-types of Recif Island (produced at 1m resolution). The numbering of ecosystem-types follows the number (I) used in the text of section III.2.

IV DISCUSSION

IV.1 Common confusions in invasion ecology

This relates to the main question asked in the Terms of Reference for this current study. Although the ‘invasive’ nature of the Sainte Marie sedge is not mentioned in any of the annual reports of “The sustainable exploitation of Sooty tern eggs in the Seychelles” (led by Chris Feare from 1994 to 2004), this has become the main preoccupation in the recent years. This can probably be explained by the fact that invasion ecology has become a dominant topic in the conservation landscape of the Seychelles during the last 2 decades (Kueffer 2006; Nevill 2009; Senterre 2009; Senterre and Dine 2021; Senterre and Henriette 2024).

As pointed out many times by the current first author, there is an important array of misconceptions when it comes to invasion ecology and practical conservation actions. The first confusion comes from the concept of “Invasive Alien Species (IAS)”, which is a very unfortunate (but still dominant) concept in which invading species (or more so, dominant species) are considered automatically as issues imported by humans and therefore “introduced” species. Consequently, any species that can become dominant ends up being considered “invasive”, and any species considered invasive ends up being considered “introduced”. The Sainte Marie sedge (*Cyperus ligularis*) is just a typical example of that (being called an IAS). Other similar examples include the consideration of *Scaevola taccada* (Vouloutye) as an IAS (erroneously), simply because it can be a dominant species in coastal environments.

Confusions on the concept of “origin status” (native vs. introduced) are also highly problematic and widespread in ecology and conservation. Many understand the origin status as the attribute of a species for a given country. Therefore, species such as Coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) must be defined as either native or exotic to e.g. the Seychelles. Consequently, scientists debate endlessly on the answer, some claiming that it is native and others claiming that this is nonsense and the species is obviously introduced. In fact, the correct answer to that question is that *Cocos nucifera* is both native and introduced to the Seychelles as an administrative unit. Therefore the two opposite points of view defended by the two opposing groups of scientists are in fact both true, which explains the impossibility to have a resolution of those kinds of debates. The correct approach is to enquire the origin status of a species not for an administrative area, but rather for a biogeographic entity (broadly) and/or for a given (sub)population (locally). In the same example, *Cocos nucifera* (which is native to Seychelles as a country) has to be considered as an “introduced” species to Recif Island. And the question of the origin status has to be explored independently of the question on the “invasive” status.

In conclusion, even though the Sainte Marie sedge is a dominant species on the hill of Recif Island, it is a mistake to automatically conclude that the sedge has to be spreading (invading) and that it has to be an IAS (i.e. introduced by humans on Recif) and, furthermore, that it leads to a decline of the bird population. Below, we will enquire those questions based on observed facts.

IV.2 Is the Sainte Marie sedge ‘invasive’ on Recif Island?

The first description of the vegetation of Recif is provided by Malavois (1787). It describes an island already treeless. The other few descriptions available (Ridley and Percy 1958; Feare and Gill 1994; Feare 2002) all describe a vegetation pattern that appears similar to the current state of the island. The Sainte Marie sedge, itself, is clearly a native species in Seychelles and it is generally associated with either coastal environments (in the Outer Islands) or bird populations

(Fosberg and Renvoize 1980; Seychelles Key Biodiversity Areas National Coordination Group 2022).

Therefore, it is clear that the Sainte Marie sedge has covered the granitic hill of Recif since before the arrival of humans in Seychelles. It is native to Recif, on the one hand, and there is no clear indication from the literature on its eventual spread or increased dominance, on the other.

To explore further this question, we have studied evidence provided by the BCM team (since 1994). The first qualitative evaluation available is found in the annual report of 1995 (Feare and Gill 1995) which describes “80% of ground cover” in the sedge grassland. In the annual report of 2002 (Feare 2002), the author describes “tussocks up to c. 0.5 m tall with bare soil or stones between them”. In 2006, when the second author of this report was involved in the work on Recif, we have a large number of photographs that allow a visual comparison with our recent observations (almost 20 years later). However, the major challenge is related to the seasonality in the sedge meadow biomass: maximal at the end of the rainy season (February) and minimal at the peak of nesting of the Sooty terns (in May-July). In Figure 16, looking at photographs from the highest density area of the hill, the sedge meadow appears just a little bit shorter in 2006 compared to 2024. However, the comparison does not allow to account for the seasonality effects and therefore it is not possible to detect a clear change in the sedge height and ground cover from 2006 to now. Indeed, in Figure 13, we can see the impact of nesting birds’ presence on the sedge meadow during a single season and within the same type of soil and topography.

Figure 16. Comparison of the Sainte Marie sedge meadow density and height in June 2006 (top left photo), during the Sooty tern nesting season, and in October 2024 (top right and bottom photos), outside of the nesting season.

Besides the discussion on the possible development (ground cover and height) of the sedge grassland, another interesting element to look at is the size of the *Nephrolepis* patches. Indeed, if the vegetation is developing with more biomass (due to climatic and/or ornithogenic aspects), the diameter of the fern patches (supposedly progressing onto the sedge meadow) can be something much easier to measure compared to the ground cover and height of the sedge.

Although *Nephrolepis biserrata* (Fouzer taba) was observed only near granite boulders in Feare (2002), Gendron (2006) clearly mapped the same patches that we observed in the highest sedge density area of the hill (on gentle non-rocky slope). It is therefore not clear if those patches were present or not in 2002 and earlier. Nevertheless, we have physically walked all around the edges of the main patches during our field work, using GPS tracking, and this provides very strong data to compare with the exact outline of the fern patches as observed on the aerial image provided by the government (from 2010, at 0.5m resolution). The Figure 17 indicates clearly a progression of the fern patch over the sedge meadow. The largest patch progressed from 25 to 44m in diameter (corresponding to a progression of 9.5m in all directions), and the second largest patch (a little bit further down the slope) progressed from 15 to 34m in diameter (also corresponding to 9.5m in all directions).

Therefore, we conclude that there is unquestionably an observed progression (development) of the vegetation of the gentle non-rocky slopes of Recif Island. This means that even though we do not have clear evidence that the sedge meadow has become denser and higher, we can assume that it has to some extent. We can also assume that the fernland will continue progressing, at least in that area of the hill, corresponding to the most favorable topo-edaphic conditions. However, the fern *Nephrolepis biserrata* is also not to be considered as an “invasive” species (and much less an “IAS”).

Figure 17. Illustration of the expansion (progression) of the fern patches located on the gentle slope near the summit of Recif Island. The background aerial image was captured in 2010, and the patches of the fern are clearly visible in dark green. The blue lines represent all our GPS tracking, including the tracking of the outline of the largest fern patches. It therefore shows unquestionably a significant progression.

IV.3 Is the Sooty tern population declining on Recif Island?

After discussing the progression of the vegetation on the main hill area, the logical assumption is to suppose that such change can impact the attractivity of the site for the nesting of the Sooty terns, leading to the decrease of the observed population. However, we have shown that the Sainte Marie sedge is not an invasive species and was ‘always’ there. The observed progression is therefore not the result of a sudden anthropogenic invasion. This leaves us with two possible explanations that are not mutually exclusive. Firstly, the known overfishing related to the tuna industry in the Western Indian Ocean can be the dominant factor causing the decline of the Sooty tern population (Feare et al. 2007; Jaquemet et al. 2007), which in turn can reduce the ornithogenic effects (trampling, feces deposits, etc.) and lead to the progression of the vegetation. Secondly, the global climate change might involve an increased rainfall on Recif, which can also contribute to the progression of the vegetation in the areas with the highest topographic wetness. Although we have no data on the rainfall of Recif, there is a lot more evidence supporting the first hypothesis.

However, it is important to note that monitoring of the seabird colonies on Recif has been primarily for the protection against poaching, and the monitoring data in circular plots (counting eggs in plots of 1.78m radius, i.e. 10m²/plot) is either incomplete or not analyzed for the time series. Therefore, although the reduction of the Sooty tern colonies is observed in many sites (Feare et al. 2007; Jaquemet et al. 2007), it has not been confirmed for Recif.

IV.4 Discussing the seabird – vegetation interaction

A review of the literature on seabird colonies nesting in tussock grasslands provided little quantitative material (no data on the grassland biomass). However, in an example from South Georgia (in polar environment; Figure 18), we can clearly see an increased height and ground cover. Therefore, in the humid tropics, it is clear that even a smaller decrease in bird population could lead to a greater change in the grassland biomass (supporting our observations).

Figure 18. Illustration of the decline of a seabird population corresponding to a reduction of over 75% in about 40 years (here the Grey-headed albatrosses on Bird Island, South Georgia: <https://appliedecologistsblog.com/2019/08/15/fishery-risk-zones-for-seabird-populations/>, British Antarctic Survey). The impact on the grassland is clearly visible but can hardly be quantified visually.

If the effect of declining bird population over grassland biomass is clear, the opposite is not necessarily obvious. Although Sooty terns have a preference for open environments with rather small grasses interspaced with bare soil areas (Saliva and Burger 1989; Ascension Island Government 2015), they have a remarkable adaptability to different context (Feare et al. 1997). In 2002, Feare (2002, p. 10) reported the result of an experiment where 10 circular plots (1.78m radius) had been cleared from the sedge (just before the nesting season) and 10 other plots were used as ‘control’. Although it is possible that the plots were too small (edge effects), this experiment resulted in the same egg densities in the two groups. It is therefore less likely that the seabird population is declining because of the vegetation progression, but rather more likely the opposite, i.e. the vegetation progressing because of the seabird decline, itself most likely related primarily to the fishing industry.

However, it is also possible that, above a certain threshold of grassland biomass (density and height), the vegetation does indeed lose attractiveness for the birds.

IV.5 Proposed experimental design for further study

The most important, and most interesting questions to explore are:

1. What is the effect of the sedge grassland density on the Sooty terns habitat suitability?
2. What is the progression of the sedge grassland in terms of biomass?

Exploring those questions on Recif Island is essential, and this holds to the unique configuration of that island, where the Sooty terns nest in a non-coastal, quite stable grassland that has remained in a natural condition throughout its history (except for the extirpation of the giant land tortoises). Therefore, identifying and quantifying a decline in the Sooty tern population would provide a good indication to the part of the general decline of Sooty terns due to the fishing industry (as other usual factors involved, such as vegetation or land use, remained constant on Recif, and as poaching or other egg harvesting is reduced to the minimum).

1. Bird-grassland density experiment

In order to test the effect of the grassland density, we suggest the following experimental design: Figure 19.

Figure 19. Proposed experimental design for the testing of vegetation management options and their effect on the habitat suitability for the nesting of the Sooty terns. In the low and moderate density treatments, we propose to cut a defined proportion of the Sainte Marie sedge tussocks (with a brush cutter, just before the beginning of the nesting season, i.e. in February): A: 100% cut; B: no cut; C: 50-70% cut. Subsequently, during the nesting season, at the usual time, circular plots will be done to quantify the nesting bird density in each treatment area, using 6 circular plots near the edges and 6 circular plots close to the centre.

Figure 20. Spatial distribution of the 4 different experiments suggested in the text.

Checklist:

-In February, bring a brush cutter with metal blade; make sure it is either new or completely cleaned and disinfected (for biosecurity reasons, such as the established risk of spread of invasive fern spores from Mahé: Senterre & Dine 2021). Cut just above ground level 100% of the sedge tussocks in the area A, and 50-60% in the area C. Probably just leave the cut materials in place (depending on field-based decision).

-Before implementing the cutting, clearly mark the experimental zones using 1.2m high metal poles. Two 25 by 75m candidate zones have been identified in the field in October 2024. Only one of them needs to be chosen. The delineation needs to be fine-tuned (but still approximately) using a pair of 50m measuring tapes.

-In June, sample the 36 circular plots (1.78m radius, counting eggs) as shown in Figure 19. For each circular plot, take GPS coordinates, a photograph, and note the estimated ground cover by vegetation, rock cover, and the maximum height of the sedges.

2. *Nephrolepis progression experiment*

A simple experiment could provide highly precise data on the suggested progression of the fern patches (so far identified based on the comparison of past aerial image and ground data). This consists simply in putting a 1.2m high metal pole at the exact edge of the fern patch, at four different places: upslope, downslope, and perpendicularly to the left and right sides.

Checklist:

- Take the coordinates of each pole
- Tag each pole with a unique code e.g. '1', '2', '3', '4', using an aluminium tag
- Take a photograph of the fern-sedge transition at the pole
- Every year, measure the position of the fern-sedge transition relative to the position of each pole (using positive values outwardly and negative values inwardly).

3. *Sainte Marie sedge biomass experiment*

Considering that we suspect a currently increasing biomass of the sedge grassland, regardless of the study of management options, we have to verify that supposed trend using measurements. This can represent a relatively simple experiment (compared to the potential benefit).

Checklist:

- Pick a site nearby experiment 1 (at least 10m away from its edges) with dense sedge grassland.
- Measure exactly 1m² and cut all 'above ground biomass' within that square meter.
- Take the exact GPS coordinates and photographs (before and after cutting).
- Carefully pick all the cut fragments and place them safely in a bag well closed (use a non-plastic bag that lets humidity get out, such as those used in small shops on Mahé).
- Let dry to the sun and store safely to bring back to Mahé.
- Weight precisely the dried plant material.
- Replicate this for 4 or 5 (up to 10) square meter plots.
- Do the same thing for the same number of plots but within the area 'A' of experiment 1 (do it just before cutting the sedge for the purpose of experiment 1).
- Repeat the experiment every 3 or 5 years (using different spots from the previous implementation)

4. *Sainte Marie sedge reduction techniques*

If the previous experiment shows that reducing the density of the sedge can improve the habitat suitability for the Sooty terns, then we will have to enquire the best technique for reducing the density of the sedge. Beside using a brush cutter, which might require more regular maintenance, we can also imagine using a pickaxe to uproot the defined proportion of tussocks.

For example, in Feare (2002, p.5), "Selby Remie reported results of an experiment on the management of Zepi Ble *Stachytarpheta jamaicensis* that indicated that pulling and leaving the plants, or pulling and removing them, led to higher nest densities of sooty terns than trampling, cutting or slashing the plants". It is therefore likely that the technique used to reduce the sedge density can have a significant impact on the egg density.

Checklist:

- Pick a site nearby experiment 1 (at least 10m away from its edges) with dense sedge grassland.
- Try to uproot 50% of the tussock over an area of about 4 by 4m.
- Take photographs before and after.
- Take a photograph every year to see the vegetation changes.

V CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

Here we compile the main findings of this study, in relation to the objectives defined in our Terms of Reference, and we summarize a few ideas for further study.

The first botanical survey and ecosystem description for Recif Island

Maybe because of its remoteness, small size, and absence of trees, Recif Island has received very little attention (except for the study of seabirds). Only 7 plant species records existed before this study. Following the collection of 20 new specimens, during the current study, we raised the total number of species to 19. Descriptions of the vegetation and terrestrial ecosystems had been done in 2002 by Chris Feare and 2006 by Gilberte Gendron (both fauna experts). We put those studies into perspective for the first time here by complementing them with a botanical and vegetational expertise. In addition, we integrate our analysis into the Global Ecosystem Typology now being used as the global standard by the IUCN.

Sainte Marie sedge is native and non-invasive

Not all dominant species are “invasive” (some ecosystem-types are naturally pauci- or even monospecific). Not all invasive species are “aliens”, IAS, Invasive Alien Species (some native invasive species can also be invasive). Based on a careful analysis of the vegetation and data on Recif Island, we suggest that the Sainte Marie sedge is neither invasive, nor exotic on Recif. On the contrary, it is likely that the granitic hill of that island has been covered by the same monospecific grassland for centuries or more.

Inland grasslands on gentle slope are progressing

The ecology of the granitic hill of Recif indicates that the climax vegetation is likely a *Pisonia*-dominated forest. Its geomorphology and geology even suggest that it must have been covered by such forests at some point during the Quaternary (the last million, year or even more), in association with seabirds (although probably not the Sooty terns). Long before the arrival of humans, the forests of Recif were extirpated and the sedge grassland that we know today was established, along with the population of Sooty terns. Since then, although the climate of the last few millennia is favorable to the redevelopment of the forest, the grassland has persisted due to the birds engineering, or ornithogenic effect on the vegetation (which suppress the redevelopment in biomass). However, our study suggests that, currently, the gentle non-rocky slopes of the hill are progressing slowly, which suggests a reduced ornithogenic pressure.

The impact of vegetation changes on Sooty terns is not established

It has been shown in the literature that the Sooty terns can be quite adaptive with regards to their nesting habitat. Based on the current data available, it is not possible to evaluate the potential change of attractivity of the habitat in relation to the increasing biomass of some of the grassland areas.

An experimental design is proposed to address the key knowledge gaps

To address the main knowledge gap described above, we have imagined and described an experimental design. This is the result of personal discussions with Sooty tern experts such as Chris Feare. The value of such experimental study could have an impact far beyond the strict

management of Recif. Indeed, Recif being largely ‘pristine’, without known or foreseen habitat-loss, and with limited illegal egg harvesting, provides the perfect site for the study of the hypothesized role of fishing industry over the reduction of the population of Sooty terns (since it is decorrelated from the other two main factors).

The flora and ecosystem-types need complementary field study

Grasslands and sparsely vegetated ecosystems can have seasonal species that disappear at some periods of the year. It is therefore important to complement our field visit with another one, to be done ideally at the end of the rainy season (e.g. in late February).

In addition, to improve our understanding of ecosystem-types, it would be very useful to make more observations on the plateau (using transects, to be done at the lowest bird population presence), as well as on the pedologic profile of the Inland mesic grasslands ([8]). Further exploration of the bare soil stretch located at the transition between the plateau and the hill is also advisable.

Existing data on Sooty tern monitoring since 2006 needs to be analyzed for Recif

The hypothesized reduction of the Sooty tern colony on Recif island needs to be verified using the monitoring data collected (mostly since 2006). A graph of the egg density per year needs to be produced, eventually accounting for expected natural variations due to ‘El Niño’ years (Molina-Montenegro et al. 2013).

Recif Island is a unique site in the granitic group and deserves more attention

The most striking feature of Recif Island is its geomorphology. In some places, one may get the impression to be on Aldabra, with limestone raised at least 1m above the high sea level, with fossilized mangrove footprints here, and fossilized coral there, indicating the remains of a paleo-reef. Studies on such features have provided very important data on the paleo-ecology of the Seychelles in general (and beyond) (Dutton et al. 2015; Hume et al. 2018; Braithwaite 2020). Similar studies on Recif could bring a unique insight into the paleo-ecology of the granitic Seychelles.

Finally, considering the remarkable state of conservation of the island, it is also important to bring specialists of other taxonomic groups, especially for the update on the Arachnids, and other invertebrates.

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VII ANNEXES

Annex 1. Summary of all non-plant species observed and posted on iNaturalist– Beecological account (by Gilberte Gendron). More generally, the latter author took 187 photos of landscapes, 119 of and 134 of fauna.

Taxon	Phylum	Class	Order	Genus	Scientific name	Common name
Animalia	Arthropoda	Hexanauplia	Balanomorpha		Balanidae	Balanidae
				Coenobita	<i>Coenobita rugosus</i>	Tawny Hermit Crab
				Eriphia	<i>Eriphia sebana</i>	Smooth Red-eyed Crab
				Geograpsus	<i>Geograpsus crinipes</i>	Yellow Nipper
				Geograpsus	<i>Grapsus sp</i>	Karkasay
Arachnida	Arthropoda	Arachnida	Araneae		Araneae	Spiders
Aves	Chordata	Aves	Charadriiformes	Anous	<i>Anous tenuirostris</i>	Lesser Noddy
				Arenaria	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	Ruddy Turnstone
				Gygis	<i>Gygis alba</i>	White Tern
				Onychoprion	<i>Onychoprion anaethetus</i>	Bridled Tern
			Onychoprion	<i>Onychoprion fuscatus</i>	Sooty Tern	
			Passeriformes	Foudia	<i>Foudia madagascariensis</i>	Red Fody
			Phaethontiformes	Phaethon	<i>Phaethon lepturus</i>	White-tailed Tropicbird
Procellariiformes	Ardenna	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Wedge-tailed Shearwater			
Chromista	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae			Phaeophyceae	Brown algae
Insecta	Arthropoda	Insecta	Coleoptera	Cratopus	Cratopus	Cratopus
				Oryctes	<i>Oryctes monoceros</i>	African Rhinoceros Beetle
				Protaetia	<i>Protaetia aurichalcea</i>	Protaetia aurichalcea
			Diptera	Lucilia	Lucilia	Greenbottle Flies
					Oestroidea	Bot Flies, Blow Flies, and Allies
					Formicidae	Ants
Mollusca	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cycloneritida		Neritidae	Nerite Snails
			Littorinimorpha		Littorininae	Littorininae
			Neogastropoda	Tenguella	Tenguella	Tenguella
				Cellana	Cellana	Indo-Pacific Limpets
Reptilia	Chordata	Reptilia	Squamata	Trachylepis	<i>Trachylepis sechellensis</i>	Seychelles Skink
			Squamata	Trachylepis	<i>Trachylepis wrightii</i>	Wright's Mabuya